

Personalized Periodontics - Personalized Care For Perfect Smiles

Kurinchichelvan Ramalingam¹, Narayane Ramkumar², Saravanakumar Ravindran³
S. Sakthidevi⁴, Vanathy Desingu⁵, Kavitha Ragu⁶

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Senior Lecturer¹
Department of Periodontology
Indira Gandhi Institute of Dental Sciences
Sri Balaji Vidyapeeth
(Deemed to be University)
Puducherry, India

Senior Lecturer²
Department of Periodontology
Indira Gandhi Institute of Dental Sciences
Sri Balaji Vidyapeeth
(Deemed to be University)
Puducherry, India.

Professor & HOD³
Department of Periodontology
Indira Gandhi Institute of Dental Sciences
Sri Balaji Vidyapeeth
(Deemed to be University)
Puducherry, India

Professor⁴
Department of Periodontology
Indira Gandhi Institute of Dental Sciences
Sri Balaji Vidyapeeth
(Deemed to be University)
Puducherry, India

Senior Lecturer⁵
Department of Periodontology
Indira Gandhi Institute of Dental Sciences
Sri Balaji Vidyapeeth
(Deemed to be University)
Puducherry, India

Post Graduate Student⁶
Department of Public Health Dentistry
KLE VK Institute of Dental Sciences
KLE Academy of Higher Education &
Research
Belagavi, India

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Introduction

A new era of precision and individualized care is going to dawn in the medical and dental industries. This century will see a major shift in the delivery of dental healthcare.

To really appreciate customized dentistry, one must comprehend this change in historical perspective. The primary treatment modality in dentistry has experienced several notable transitions over the years. The first was the extraction-based dentistry era, which was pioneered by Pierre Fauchard. The second stage of dentistry, known as restorative and replacement-based dentistry, got underway in 1728 with the publication of Fauchard's revolutionary book *Le Chirurgien Dentiste*. The field of preventative dentistry began to take shape around 1945 when fluoride dentistry became prominent.¹

The goal of personalized medicine is to develop oral healthcare regimens, treatments, and/or supplies that are particular to each patient. An expansion of personalized care known as "P4 medicine" includes participatory, preventative, customized, and predictive components. Leroy Hood coined the phrase "P4 medicine" more than five years ago to describe the continuous shift in medicine from a specialty focused on treating patients' illnesses to one that is proactive and maximizes each patient's well-being.^{2,3}

A predictive method will make it possible to identify those who are at-risk and diagnose periodontitis early on, when successful treatment is easier to handle, by

applying modern diagnostic procedures.

The concept of Participatory Periodontology, in which networked individuals take a leadership role in their own health care, will be introduced to highlight the patient's active participation.

It is a customized prevention based on the microbiological and genetic makeup of a specific patient.

A sophisticated approach to periodontal care, personalized periodontics adjusts preventative and treatment plans to meet the specific requirements of each patient. Personalized periodontics uses a mix of precise patient information, including genetic, clinical, and lifestyle characteristics, to generate customized treatment programs, in contrast to standard periodontics, which frequently employs a one-size-fits-all paradigm.⁴

Principles of Personalized Periodontics

To determine each patient's specific needs for oral health, a thorough examination is performed in personalized periodontics. This could include:

1. Genetic Testing: Determining genetic susceptibilities to periodontal disease can assist in risk assessment and customized prevention strategies.
2. Clinical Evaluation: A thorough assessment of the teeth, gums, and general oral health, encompassing bone density, attachment levels, and periodontal pockets measurements.
3. Assessment of Lifestyle and Behavior: Taking into account variables that can affect periodontal health, such as nutrition, smoking status, and dental cleanliness routines.

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4. Risk Assessment: Assessing individual risk factors that could influence the course of periodontal disease, such as systemic health issues (like diabetes).⁵

The objective is to convert the current reactive therapeutic perspective which considers tissue degradation to be clinically detectable into a predictive, future perspective that envisions early illness detection during the subclinical stage.

Using This Data, Customized Periodontics Seeks to Offer

Preventive Care: Using specific risk factor-based tactics, develop ways to stop the development or progression of periodontal disease.

Tailored Care Programs: Make individualized treatment plans that cater to the particular requirements of the patient. These plans may involve regenerative techniques, laser treatments, or more accurate scaling and root planing.

Ongoing Monitoring: Make sure the treatment plan is regularly reviewed and modified in accordance to the patient's reaction and any changes in their condition.

Genetic Factors

The knowledge that hereditary variables significantly influence a person's susceptibility to periodontal disease is one of the pillars of individualized periodontics. Genetic variants linked to an elevated risk of periodontal disease have been found in several investigations. For instance, an increased risk of developing severe periodontitis has been associated with polymorphisms in the interleukin-1 (IL-1) gene cluster. Clinicians can identify patients who are at higher risk and initiate preventive treatments early on by having a better understanding of the patient's genetic propensity.

Nonetheless, there is ongoing discussion on the clinical usefulness of genetic testing in periodontics. Some contend that it can improve risk assessment and help choose the best course of therapy, while others draw attention to the fact that the majority of the illness risk is not explained by the genetic markers that have been found to yet. Moreover, genetic testing may not be widely used in standard clinical practice due to its high cost and limited accessibility.⁶

Analysis of the Microbiome

Another significant part of individualized periodontics is the examination of the oral microbiome. An intricate collection of bacteria called the oral microbiome is essential to preserving dental health. Periodontal disease has been related to dysbiosis, or an imbalance in the microbial ecology.

Recent developments in high-throughput sequencing technologies have allowed for a detailed analysis of the oral microbiome's composition. Antimicrobial therapy may be more successfully tailored if particular bacteria profiles linked to periodontal disease are identified. For instance, focused antimicrobial therapies rather than broad-spectrum antibiotics may be beneficial for a patient whose microbiome is dominated by specific pathogenic microorganisms.

Nonetheless, there is a complicated and incomplete understanding of the connection between periodontal disease and the microbiome. Although microbiome analysis is still in its infancy and needs more research to be implemented in

therapeutic settings, it has the potential to provide tailored treatment.⁷

Discovery of Biomarkers

Biomarkers have the potential to be important in customized periodontics since they are quantifiable indications of a biological state or condition. Biomarkers can be used to track the effectiveness of treatment, identify periodontal disease, and forecast how the condition will progress.

For instance, active periodontal disease has been linked to increased levels of certain inflammatory cytokines in the saliva or gingival crevicular fluid.

Finding trustworthy biomarkers may make it possible to develop more focused treatment plans and accurate diagnoses. For example, a patient may benefit from more severe anti-inflammatory therapy if they have elevated levels of a certain biomarker. Periodontal biomarkers are still being developed and validated, and there are difficulties in guaranteeing their precision, dependability, and clinical applicability.⁸

The Challenges and Limitations of Customized Periodontics

Personalized periodontics is an intriguing concept, but before it can be implemented in clinical settings, a number of issues and restrictions must be resolved.

Complexity of Periodontal Disease

Multiple variables, including genetic, environmental, microbiological, and immunological components, can contribute to periodontal disease. The intricate interactions among these variables pose a challenge in creating a straightforward, customized treatment plan. For instance, disparities in dental hygiene habits, smoking status, or other environmental factors may cause two patients with similar genetic risk factors to experience different disease outcomes.

Treatment may also be made more difficult by the fact that periodontal disease frequently coexists with other systemic diseases like diabetes or cardiovascular disease. These comorbidities may call for a more comprehensive strategy to patient management that incorporates customized medicine in general with individualized periodontics specifically.⁹

Social and Ethical Aspects to Consider

Several ethical and societal issues are brought up by the use of individualized periodontics. Although biomarker analysis and genetic testing might yield insightful results, they also give rise to worries over data security, privacy, and potential prejudice. For instance, there can be issues with employers or insurance firms using genetic data.

Moreover, the cost of tailored periodontics, including genetic testing and microbiome analysis, may limit access to these treatments, potentially worsening existing health disparities. As the field advances, ensuring fair access to individualized periodontal care will be crucial.

Five layers make up a futuristic way of diagnosing periodontal disease.

Level I diagnostics: Lab-on-a-chip [LOC]

Cone beam computed tomography, and gas chromatographs

With the use of contemporary diagnostic tools, periodontists

can:

1. Find a lesion in the periodontal tissue before it manifests clinically; and
2. Identify the "Active Phase" of periodontitis.

A device that integrates many laboratory tasks onto a single millimeter sized chip is called a lab-on-a-chip (LOC). LOCs handle microfluidics, which are extremely small fluid volumes that are less than picolitres. The technology underlying a novel tiny analysis system for biological applications, such as single-cell gene expression profiling, proteomic analysis, sequencing, and DNA amplification, purification, and separation, is known as microfluidics.

Gas Chromatography

Halitosis is a major concern for the general populace. The term "bad breath paradox" describes the situation in which certain individuals with oral malodor are occasionally completely unaware of this fact, while others experience halitosis even in the absence of an identifiable reason. Salivary stagnation causes physiological halitosis, or "morning breath," which disappears when you eat, drink, or brush your teeth.

Cone Beam Computed Tomography

First introduced in the European market in 1996, the technology known as cone beam computed tomography (CBCT) was first introduced in the US market in 2001. CBCT uses a cone-shaped beam to scan the entire image in one rotation. As the scanner rotates around the subject, a CBCT scan can yield up to almost 600 different images. The scanning program collects the anatomical data and then uses specialist software to build a digital volume consisting of three-dimensional voxels that can be seen and edited. The outcome is a cleaner image with no information gaps.

Level 2 Diagnostics

Genetic vulnerability

Most studies demonstrate no correlation between the studied SNPs and the presence of disease indicators for either the chronic or aggressive forms of periodontitis. The SNPs that seemed to be associated with periodontitis in different ethnic groups were tied to the Fc-gamma receptor genes. However, both aggressive and chronic periodontitis were associated with these variants of the same gene.

A composite genotype consisting of two polymorphic loci-interleukin-1A (-889) and interleukin-1B (+3954)-that are single nucleotide polymorphisms carrying a C-T transition was described by Kornman et al. in 1997. However, the analysis of the interleukin-1A (+4845) G-T dimorphism, which revealed that the two loci that make up the genotype linked to periodontitis were in linkage disequilibrium, rendered interleukin-1A (-889) obsolete.

Level 3 of Diagnosis

Bacterial Infection

Six categories of lines of evidence were proposed by Haffajee and Socransky to bolster the theory that microorganisms have an aetiological function in periodontal infections:

1. A higher disease odds ratio.

2. The transformation of illness into wellness upon the inhibition of microorganisms.
3. The emergence of a host reaction.
4. The virulence factors are present.
5. Proof from research on animals supporting the findings in human subjects.
6. Backing from research on risk assessment.

Levels 4 And 5 of Diagnosis

Host reaction components and compounds produced from tissue breakdown:

Currently, established molecules linked to mediators of tissue degradation and host response variables have been suggested as diagnostic biomarkers for periodontitis. Numerous dental societies, including the American Dental Association (ADA), applaud the development of quick point-of-care assays that offer precise measurements of clinically validated biomarkers and acknowledge the necessity of ongoing research on oral fluid diagnostics.

Oral Fluid as A Diagnostic Tool

Oral fluid is a multipurpose, watery material that is perhaps the most basic organic diagnostic tool available. The composition of oral fluid, or entire saliva, is 99.5% water and 0.5% antibacterial chemicals. The benefits of employing oral fluid as a diagnostic medium for quick point-of-care testing include patient acceptance, ease of use, and non-invasive sample collection.

The fluid that is extracted from the mouth during expectoration is known as oral fluid (also known as entire saliva). Gingival crevicular fluid and glandular-duct saliva are included.

1. Glandular duct saliva: Using specially made collectors, saliva released by the parotid, sub-mandibular, sublingual, and minor salivary glands (2,000 ml/24 h) is collected straight from the glandular ducts. The majority of the IgA in glandular-duct saliva is secretory.
2. An exudate (0.5 to 2.5 ml/24 h) flushes from the gingival sulcus is known as gingival crevicular fluid (GCF). GCF is a flexible and non-invasive method for taking samples of the oral cavity's biomarkers of inflammation and bone resorption. Serum components are represented by GCF, which is layered with byproducts of regional physiological or pathological processes. Specifically, pathologic conditions including bone loss and connective tissue degradation might be useful for diagnosis. Even if reactants must be extremely sensitive because biomarkers are more diluted, it seems that using entire saliva is more practicable, even though gingival crevicular fluid is the most suitable diagnostic medium to utilize in analyses.¹⁰

Salivary Biomarkers for Periodontal Disease

A group of three study groups recently disclosed the full human salivary proteome, which found that 1,166 proteins are found in human saliva. More than sixty-five GCF components have been investigated as potential indicators of the advancement of periodontitis. These elements can be divided into three broad groups:

Beta-glucuronidase, Cathepsin B, MMP-8 (collagenase-2), MMP-9 (gelatinase), Dipeptidyl peptidases II and IV, Elastase, and RANKL are examples of host-derived enzymes. OPG, RANK, and RANKL are examples of host response modifiers. Tissue breakdown products include 1-CTP and C-4-S.

Consequences for the Future

There are difficulties associated with the growth of customized periodontics. Personalized care implementation necessitates sophisticated diagnostic instruments, in-depth knowledge of genetic and systemic determinants, and the capacity to incorporate these components into clinical practice. Furthermore, in order to guarantee the accuracy and application of genetic testing and other diagnostic techniques, further study is required.

The ramifications of individualized periodontics are significant, notwithstanding these difficulties. It represents a shift in dental care toward a more comprehensive and patient-centered strategy. A new benchmark for periodontal care is established by customized periodontics, which incorporates genetic, clinical, lifestyle, and systemic data to tailor treatment to each patient's specific needs.

Conclusion

Personalized periodontics is a major development in dental care that goes beyond standard treatment plans to provide more individualized and efficient periodontal disease management. This method improves patient outcomes, tailors treatment programs, and strengthens preventative care by taking into account the complex characteristics of each patient's genetic profile, clinical condition, lifestyle, and general health conditions. Personalized periodontics is positioned to revolutionize dental care in the future as science and technology continue to progress, highlighting the movement in medicine towards a more accurate and customized approach.

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